

DEVELOPING A JAPANESE LANGUAGE TEACHING MATERIAL MODEL FOR NURSING INTERNSHIP PROGRAM STUDENTS IN JAPANESE NURSING HOMES: A RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT STUDY

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Abstract

Background: The increasing demand for healthcare nurses in Japan has prompted the Bethesda Tomohon Nursing Education Institution to address this challenge through an internship program. To meet the program's language proficiency requirements, students are equipped with Japanese language skills equivalent to N4 (level 4), focusing on Japanese for specific purposes. **Objective:** This research aims to develop Japanese language teaching materials for students participating in the internship program at a Japanese nursing home. **Methods:** The Research and Development method, guided by Borg and Gall's stage design, is employed in this study involving 22 participants engaged in internship activities. The stages include needs analysis (students, teachers, and graduate users), design, development of teaching material models, expert feasibility testing, and model effectiveness testing. Data collection methods encompass observation, surveys, interviews, and experiments, with text data qualitatively described and experimental data subjected to inferential statistical tests. **Results:** The needs analysis results, triangulated across three different objects, indicate a collective demand for teaching materials tailored to the specific field of expertise, namely nursing. The developed teaching material model proves highly effective, as evidenced by posttest results in the experimental class (average score: 81.61) compared to Akper's teaching materials (average score: 66.39). A t-test, conducted using both SPSS 25, revealed a significant difference in average student learning outcomes between conventional and developed teaching materials; t-value of 4.595 surpassed the critical t-value of 2.021 at a significance level of 0.05 with degrees of freedom equal to 34. The average learning outcomes of students using the developed materials surpassed those using Akper's materials, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H₀) in favor of the alternative hypothesis (H_a). These findings indicate a high level of effectiveness for the tested teaching materials. **Conclusions:** In conclusion, the developed Japanese Nursing teaching materials are deemed feasible and effective for Nursing students in internship programs at Japanese Nursing Homes. The research recommends comprehensive needs-based instructional material development. Additionally, the study suggests the applicability of the developed Japanese language teaching materials in other nursing institutions, fostering independent learning and enhancing student motivation.

Keywords: Japanese Teaching Material; Internship; Japan Nursing Home.

INTRODUCTION

The need for nursing personnel increases every year also due to the problem of the aging population (Arai et al., 2015; Evans, 2018; Maben & Bridges, 2020; Song & Tang, 2019). This situation is an opportunity for both nursing students and for institutions to hold programs internships (Efendi et al., 2021; Suzuki & Nishigori, 2018; Zerwic et al., 2020). This is in line with the opinion of (Sin, 2014) that internship has also been applied more broadly to educational programs such as; international business, nursing, health, and engineering.

Currently, the Nursing Academy "Bethesda" Tomohon collaborates with the "South Wind" Foundation to train proficient Japanese-speaking staff. Students from the Nursing Academy "Bethesda" Tomohon (referred to as AKPER Bethesda students) are being prepared as prospective interns for nursing homes in Japan.

To date, Bethesda AKPER, through the "South Wind" Foundation, has dispatched 22 interns, showcasing the students' enthusiasm for this program, with numerous registrations each year. Participation not only allows students to apply their knowledge but also positions them for potential permanent employment post-graduation. Additionally, internship participants receive financial support to aid in their studies.

Graduates from Bethesda AKPER are well-prepared for internships in various nursing homes, hospitals, and companies in Japan. Prior to the program's implementation, prospective practical students must possess proficiency in Japanese to meet work requirements and effectively communicate with the elderly, colleagues, and integrate into the local community and environment. To fulfill these expectations, students must attain Japanese language skills aligned with the competency standards set by users (Kayaoğlu & Akbaş, 2016). For participants in the internship program, Japanese language proficiency equivalent to N4 level (Nihongo nouryoku level 4) is required. Furthermore, AKPER graduates participating in the work internship program must hold an N4 pass certificate. Japanese language education for practical or internship candidates focuses on equipping participants with various language skills relevant to work in nursing homes or hospitals.

In connection with that, so that learning objectives can be met, it is necessary to prepare and equip with good teaching materials, namely those that are in accordance with the needs in their field of work, namely language for special purposes or Japanese for specific purposes, or appropriate teaching materials especially related to the content of the subject matter (Kim et al., 2016; Richards, 2015; Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., & Griffin, 2010). Until now, books or teaching materials for Japanese Nursing specifically for the Internship program at Japanese Nursing Homes are still very less. Meanwhile, students who will take part in the program must meet the demands of the Japanese language skills of students participating in the Internship program which is equivalent to the ability of N4.

A good and high-quality teaching book is one that meets three categories of validity in its relationship with students, teachers, and content (Batubara, 2021; Doloksaribu & Triwiyono, 2020; Haris et al., 2023). These three categories of validity are:

- 1) Psychological validity, meaning the teaching book has met students' needs and has the potential to facilitate independent learning, directing and encouraging student autonomy to develop effective learning strategies;
- 2) Pedagogical validity, where the teaching book aligns with the skills and abilities of teachers, allowing professional educators to develop the material effectively;
- 3) Process and content validity, which involves using up-to-date methodologies based on the latest research findings, having suitable, culturally sensitive, clear, easily accessible, flexible, and comprehensive content, providing opportunities for students to interpret and encouraging higher-order critical thinking.

In order to meet and create a quality learning process, it is necessary to provide good teaching materials that can motivate students to learn and meet quality criteria.

Good teaching materials are expected to enable students to be diligent and active in constructing their knowledge in the learning environment (Coman et al., 2020; Sukarmin et al., 2021). These materials are developed through a thorough assessment process, considering the learners' needs, and are designed to motivate students to actively engage in building their own knowledge.

Needs analysis is a crucial initial step to understand students' requirements for a learning program. This understanding is essential for determining the appropriate content. The primary purpose of needs analysis is to extract information that can be applied to various contexts, perspectives, and factors that may exist in situations where a gap is identified.

Regarding learning, the analysis aims to gather sufficient information to determine whether a learning intervention is necessary. If intervention is required, information such as what material needs to be taught, the sequence, the media to be used, and the suitable delivery methods or strategies for specific participants who might be in a situation where there is a gap should be identified.

Therefore, to prevent a gap between the learners' Japanese language proficiency and the expected proficiency during future work practices, learners need to be equipped with appropriate teaching materials tailored to their needs, developed according to the principles and steps of instructional material development (Hamasaki et al., 2023; Mimura et al., 2023). Based on the background provided above, the development of a Japanese language teaching material model, especially for nursing students participating in the internship program at Japanese nursing homes, is highly necessary.

There is a similar research on the development of nursing teaching materials developed by (Bagiasa et al., 2019) which examines the development of nursing textbooks for students of class X Nursing Department at Singaraja Health Vocational School. There are similarities with this research, namely; both of them conduct research on teaching materials for special purposes, namely in the field of nursing. The difference is a different object of research. Developed nursing textbooks for students of class X Health Vocational School in Singaraja (Bagiasa et al., 2019), while this research is for nursing students more specifically for Internship program participants in Japanese Nursing Homes.

The development of teaching materials should follow and apply the principles of development which are the rules, signs, and systems that must be obeyed so that the teaching materials can be utilized and function optimally (Doloksaribu & Triwiyono, 2020; Gallegos et al., 2017; Ihsan et al., 2021). Specifically suggests six principles and criteria in the development of teaching materials such as

- 1) Teaching materials must have a clear relationship with the curriculum used,
- 2) Teaching materials must be authentic in relation to the text. and assignments
- 3) Teaching materials must encourage and foster interaction.
- 4) Teaching materials should provide opportunities for learners to focus on the formal aspects of language.
- 5) Teaching materials encourage students to develop skills in learning, dan,
- 6) Teaching materials should encourage learners to apply their skills in their real-world workplaces.

In general, the main objective of this research is to develop and produce Japanese language teaching materials for Nursing students participating in the internship program at Japanese Nursing Homes.

The above objectives are described in four objectives with details as follows:

- 1) Obtain a description of the need for the development of Japanese teaching materials for Nursing students at AKPER Bethesda Tomohon, participants in the internship program or work practice at Japanese Nursing Homes,
- 2) Produce a design model for material development teach Japanese language nursing students participating in the internship program or work practice at Japanese Nursing Homes based on needs,
- 3) Test the feasibility of teaching materials developed through expert tests, and
- 4) Mengevaluasi keefektifitasan penggunaan materi ajar yang telah dikembangkan melalui ujicoba pemakaian pada mahasiswa keperawatan peserta program *internship* di Panti Jompo Jepang.

MATERIAL & METHODS

Research Design

This research uses research and development methods with a mixed method approach (Borg, 2014). Research that is subjective or cannot be controlled, such as in terms of model development and in collecting needs analysis data obtained through observation and interviews, namely in the form of text information, a qualitative approach is used. Meanwhile, to analyze the results obtained from the distribution of questionnaires starting from the needs analysis to the implementation of teaching materials or effectiveness tests by determining the number and percentage that appear and using the t test to calculate differences in experimental results using the developed teaching materials using a quantitative approach.

The research and development of Japanese language teaching materials for students participating in the internship program follow a systematic approach based on the steps outlined by Jolly and Bolitho (1998). The process is illustrated in **Figure 1**, which represents the flowchart of the operational stages. The first phase, the Preliminary Stage, involves mapping the needs of Japanese language learning for Nursing. This includes determining materials, focus context, and skills through activities such as needs analysis, document review, and exploration of needs. The outcome is the identification of the context of focus and language categories, forming the basis for teaching material profiles. The second phase, Teaching Material Development, focuses on designing and developing teaching materials. This stage builds on the needs assessment from the preliminary stage, creating an initial draft of Japanese teaching materials. Activities include compiling and developing content based on the identified needs and determining topics aligned with the profiles and components of Japanese teaching materials for nursing. The third and final phase involves Validation, Evaluation, and Revision of the Model. This stage includes limited trials with a small group of students, followed by the revision of teaching materials based on their input. The revised materials undergo a validation or feasibility test through expert judgment, involving experts in Japanese language and teaching methodology. The model is further revised based on expert input, resulting in a draft of teaching materials II.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the Operational Stages of The Research

The implementation of the developed teaching material model involved testing its effectiveness in real classroom settings, akin to a large group trial (Field-Try out). This step aimed to yield the final product of Japanese Nursing teaching materials. Researchers conducted experiments in nursing classes, teaching directly using the developed materials. Following the completion of learning activities, a test was administered to assess the effectiveness of the teaching materials by comparing student learning outcomes using two different types of materials (before-after experimental design). The differences in results were analyzed using a t-test.

Null Hypothesis (H₀): The effectiveness of the developed teaching material model is equal to or smaller than that of the existing teaching material model. Alternative

Hypothesis (H_a): The effectiveness of the developed teaching material model is better than the existing (old) teaching material model. Or: H₀: $\mu_1 \leq \mu_2$; H_a: $\mu_1 > \mu_2$.

Additionally, in this effectiveness test, opinions of teachers and students about the developed teaching material model were gathered through questionnaires. The questionnaire covered various aspects, including content (materials and topics), methodology, readability, and design/layout of materials, compiled based on prepared guidelines. The final revision of teaching materials. Following the effectiveness test, the model underwent improvements to achieve the final product. The Japanese Nursing teaching material model, deemed suitable for use, had undergone expert tests and effectiveness tests in the classroom.

Participant

Through purposive sampling criteria, a total of n=22 Nursing students at AKPER Bethesda Tomohon participating in the internship program were involved in this research. All participants signed a consent form indicating their willingness to participate in the research activities until the end.

Procedures

Based on the results of the needs analysis and following the steps of modifying the Jolly and Bolitho Model, a Japanese language teaching material model for nursing internship programs was developed. Subsequently, the completed teaching material model underwent expert validation, effectiveness testing, and readability testing through its utilization with students.

The data sources for this research include Akper Bethesda Tomohon, where the research took place. The identified data sources consist of:

- 1) Events, namely the ongoing implementation of the Japanese language learning and teaching material model used for observation,
- 2) Informants, including students (Japanese language students) and Japanese language teachers at Akper Bethesda, and
- 3) Document data sources such as curriculum, syllabus, and current teaching materials, as well as the developed model teaching materials.

These data sources provided information on existing teaching materials, the need for materials aligned with Nursing characteristics and majors, data on the effectiveness of the developed teaching materials, and document data. Additionally, data was collected from users, specifically business actors in nursing homes in Japan who were interviewed. Furthermore, Japanese language experts were consulted to assess the developed teaching materials and provide input for improvement. The data in this study are grouped into two types, namely qualitative data and quantitative data. Qualitative data in the form of data from observations and interviews conducted by researchers directly at the research location, namely observations in Japanese language learning classrooms, and direct interviews with nursing home entrepreneurs in Japan. Other qualitative data is data in the form of input and suggestions for improvement of experts in the validation test of the described model. Quantitative data is data from needs analysis conducted through instruments in the form of questionnaires for students and teachers which are calculated as a percentage. and data on the test results of the effectiveness of teaching materials. The data on the results of the test of the effectiveness of teaching materials consists of two parts, namely:

- 1) Data on the results of the calculation of the comparison of student achievement obtained using two different types of teaching materials which were analyzed using the t-test, and
- 2) Data on the percentage of the results of the questionnaire about the effectiveness of the teaching materials distributed. to students and teachers.

The technique of checking the validity of the data in this research and development uses triangulation. In this study, the data collection technique used triangulation of data sources (ie students, teachers, nd users/entrepreneurs) and technical

triangulation through questionnaires, observations, and interviews. Furthermore, the form of data in this study uses a concurrent triangulation strategy, where the researcher collects qualitative and quantitative data concurrently (at one time) and then compares the two data to find out whether there is convergence, differences, or some combination. Needs analysis data were collected by means of observation, interviews, surveys, documentation and experiments using instruments in the form of observation guidelines, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. The observation guide contains several questions related to teaching and learning activities which are intended to determine the learning process in the classroom and the application of teaching material models, the use of curricula and syllabus, the use of media, class management, assessment, and so on. The observation guidelines used are as follows.

Measurement

Data collection techniques are carried out through observations, interviews, questionnaires, and tests where students and teachers/lecturers are the main data sources regarding the need for teaching materials, while nursing home entrepreneurs in Japan as users of graduates are complementary data sources. Sedangkan, data on the effectiveness of teaching materials were collected through questionnaires and tests filled out by students and teachers using a Likert scale after the developed teaching materials were used in class. Data on the Japanese language learning outcomes of nursing students were collected through pretest and posttest in class. After that all the data collected were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. For clearer instructions on observation, please refer to the following.

Observation Guidelines

Institution Name :
Department :
Teacher Name :
Number of Students :

- a. What are the forms of teaching materials used in class?
- b. How is the curriculum used and what form it takes?
- c. How the syllabus is used.
- d. How is the general teaching and learning process in the Japanese Internship program class?
- e. What is the teaching method used by the teacher?
- f. What is the student learning method?
- g. How is the evaluation of students' learning Japanese language skills?
- h. How are student activities in learning activities?

Furthermore, the interview guide contains several questions that are adapted to the background of the interviewee, namely nursing home entrepreneurs in Japan. The core of the question mainly concerns opinions about the basic materials or materials in textbooks as well as Japanese language competencies that are expected for a graduate. The following is an interview guide that is asked of employers of nursing

homes in Japan. This interview was conducted when the nursing home entrepreneur visited the Bethesda Tomohon Hospital in September 2020 (Mr. Kusama).

Results of Interviews (With Employers of Nursing Homes).

1. The location of the nursing home is in Tokyo
2. There are 4 (four) foreign workers in the company
3. There are two Indonesian citizens, and two Cambodians
4. Sometimes they have difficulty communicating due to lack of vocabulary mastery.
5. The company provides additional lessons.
6. Japanese language skills really need to be improved.
7. As a user, we hope that prospective nursing graduates have really learned and are equipped with knowledge of the Japanese language that is suitable for their work and have skills in the field of elderly nursing, and can write simple hiragana, katakana, and kanji, and can write job reports.

Furthermore, a questionnaire was conducted to obtain broader data on the need for teaching materials, the questionnaire that was carried out contained the criteria for learning Japanese language needs in accordance with the field of Nursing. The criteria in question are mainly about the content of the Japanese language. In addition, the questionnaire that was run for teachers was added about the quality of the model of teaching materials such as; designs and layouts, gradations, exercises, and other components, all of which are based on the compilation guidelines below (**Table 1**).

**Table 1: Guidelines for Developing Teacher and Student Opinion
 Questionnaire on Nursing Japanese Language Teaching Material Model**

No.	Principles Of Teaching Materials	No. Question
1.	Teaching materials must have a clear relationship with the curriculum used	2, 3,13
2.	There are instructions for follow-up or general progress of learning	6,10
3.	Teaching materials must encourage and foster interaction	17
4.	Teaching materials must provide opportunities for learners to focus on the formal aspects of language	10,12,14,15, 16
5.	Teaching materials encourage students to develop skills in learning	9
6.	Teaching materials must encourage students to apply their skills in the real world	13,28
7.	Teaching materials must be relevant, consistent, and sufficient.	4,
8.	Fulfilling psychological validity in the form of student needs and helping free learning and encouraging student autonomy in order to develop effective learning strategies.	9,17, 26.
9.	Meets pedagogical validity; it means that the textbook shows a sufficient measure of compatibility with the skills and abilities of the teacher	2
10	Meets process and content validity. Methodology that is up to date, the content of the material is appropriate, has appropriateness and is authentic, culturally sensitive, the layout and design is clear, easy to obtain, flexible, and complete, and can provide opportunities for students to be skilled in interpretation so that it is challenging to think higher critically.	1,7,8,10,11, 21,22,27
11.	Has the potential for affective engagement?	18, 19
12.	It can be used pleasantly by both students and teachers.	7,8,20
13.	Pay attention to the desired learning motivation	19,
14.	Following a gradual and correct sequence	5
15	There are tests that are in accordance with the material given	24,25

Furthermore, the data collection instrument for the effectiveness test was also developed based on the guidelines. To get student and teacher assessments about the effectiveness of the teaching materials developed, a questionnaire was administered to respondents using a Likert scale (rating scale). which contains four categories of choices namely; strongly agree (SS), agree (ST), disagree (KS), and disagree (TS). These guidelines are as follows:

Student Opinion Questionnaire Against

Model of Japanese Nursing Teaching Materials Developed

This questionnaire (**Table 2**) was designed with the intent to get opinions and input from students about the model of Japanese Nursing teaching materials for the Internship Program. This teaching material model was developed to improve students' Japanese language skills according to their field of nursing. For this reason, students are requested to be willing to fill out this questionnaire according to your opinion after using the teaching materials. Your opinion and input will be very meaningful and useful for improvement before being used in the next lesson in Nursing class. Thank you for your willingness.

Student Identity

Full name :
 Class/Department :
 Instruction :

Put a check mark (v) in the column that corresponds to your opinion with meaning:

SS= Strongly agree, ST= Agree, KS= Less agree, TS = Disagree.

Table 2: Student Opinion Questionnaire Against

NO.	STATEMENT	SS	ST	KS	TS
1.	Teaching Japanese at AKPER aims to equip students with foreign language skills in the field of Nursing				
2.	The teaching materials used are compatible with the Nursing major				
3.	The learning objectives are clear in the material				
4.	The formulation of objectives in the material is in accordance with the needs in the field of nursing				
5.	Learning materials are arranged and adjusted sequentially and logically				
6.	This model has clear instructions				
7.	This model is good because it contains pictures				
8.	The pictures are very appropriate to the topic/material				
9.	The forms of exercise that exist are very clear				
10.	There is a clear explanation of words and expressions				
11.	This model is authentic and in accordance with the character of students				
12.	There are four distinct language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing)				
13.	The topics are very appropriate with the majors/fields of study				
14.	Practice more conversations that are appropriate to the field of study.				
15.	The vocabulary list (Goi) is very clear				
16.	Clear grammar explanation				
17.	There are many questions to practice				

18.	There is a model or example in the conversation that makes it easier for students to remember.				
19.	This model also trains students to work together in groups				
20.	This model makes students comfortable and relaxed to study				
21.	This model guides students to find something new in the learning process				
22.	In the learning process, it provides opportunities for students to ask questions freely,				
23.	At the end of the lesson, students can reflect on the material being studied.				
24.	Assessment runs during the learning process even if it is not known by the learner				
25.	At the end of the lesson, a written assessment is also held				
26.	The students are satisfied by using this model of teaching and learning materials				
27.	Train students' independence to express and think critically.				
28.	This model is very suitable for Nursing students				

Hint II

Give your comments freely for the improvement of this model. The input you provide will be very helpful for the perfection of the Japanese Nursing teaching material model. Thank you.

Statistical Analyses

The analysis of the need for Japanese Nursing teaching materials involved data collected through a questionnaire administered to both students and teachers. The aggregated data were converted into percentages, and the higher the percentage, the greater the perceived need for a particular aspect. These percentages helped determine the level of need for each aspect, aligning with the components of teaching materials. Secondly, document data analysis was conducted in a qualitative descriptive manner, encompassing existing documents such as teaching materials and syllabi. Qualitative data, including results from document analysis, observations, or interviews, were triangulated to enhance data source credibility.

Subsequently, the process involved compiling the design of teaching material models, conducting model testing, and implementing modeling. A small group trial was conducted, and qualitative input from students was obtained in the form of free written responses. The discussion of the developed teaching material model incorporated relevant theories, particularly those related to language teaching material development.

The next phase involved an expert feasibility test, where the developed Japanese language teaching material model for nursing was evaluated by experts in Japanese language and language teaching, namely Franky R. Najoan, MA, Ph.D. The results were presented qualitatively. Following that, the effectiveness of the developed teaching materials was tested in the classroom through two methods. Firstly, after a learning experiment using the developed materials, students took a test, and a t-test was conducted to compare the results with those obtained using existing teaching materials. Secondly, a Likert scale questionnaire was used to assess readability, adequacy, suitability, etc., with students and teachers providing responses. The Likert scale results were quantified, interpreted, and presented qualitatively. All data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 25.

RESULTS

Description of the Results of the Needs Analysis, Opinions and Suggestions of Nursing Students

In the student needs analysis, the primary component revolves around Japanese Nursing teaching materials. Students are tasked with identifying the requisites for teaching materials suitable for the nursing field. The response options may encompass multiple choices, including existing ones, and students may offer additional opinions or suggestions. The choices are tabulated and subsequently elaborated upon, incorporating reasons, suggestions, and comments.

To establish a reference point, the largest percentage is considered for each instrument. Comments, suggestions, or opinions are not solely derived from individual student viewpoints but are a composite of general opinions gathered from all responses, aligning with the objectives of each item. Table 3 below presents data on student needs concerning Japanese teaching materials, highlighting the importance of materials being interesting, incorporating colorful pictures, graphics, word lists with meanings, as well as cassettes or tape recorders and videos. Notably, all respondents (100%) expressed the necessity for teaching materials to be engaging and emphasized the need for a list of words with their meanings. This table underscores the unanimous viewpoint among respondents regarding the importance of making teaching materials interesting and incorporating essential features such as visual elements, word lists, and multimedia tools.

Table 3: Results of Percentage of Student Answers to Required Aspects in Nursing Teaching Materials

Required Aspect	Total	Percentage
Interesting	18	100
Color pictures	16	88.88
Chart	3	16.66
List of Words and Their Meaning	18	100
Cassette/Tape Recorder/Video	17	94.44

Table 4 below illustrates the percentage of responses pertaining to the alignment of material content with the field of study across four language skills and other linguistic aspects. The content encompasses vocabulary, nouns, and verbs, including phrases and sentences related to daily activities.

Table 4: Percentage of Student Answers about the Need for

Required Aspect	Total	%
<i>Choukai</i> (Listening)	18	100
<i>Kaiwa</i> (Speaking is dialogue/conversation)	18	100
<i>Dokkai</i> (Read)	13	72.22
<i>Sakubun</i> (Write)	14	77.77
<i>Bunpou</i> (Grammar)	18	100
<i>Goi</i> (Vocabulary)	13	72.22

In the table above, it can be seen that almost all respondents suggested the need to include topics that are in accordance with the field or department of Nursing in all linguistic components and aspects. In the Chookai (listening) and Kaiwa (talking) sections, 100% of respondents suggested that appropriate topics/materials should be included. In the dokkai (Reading) component, 72.22% were filled in, and in the .Sakubun (Writing) component, Bunpou (Grammar), and Goi (vocabulary) also all

indicate the importance of including appropriate topics, namely 77.77%, 100%, and 72.22%, respectively.

Description of the Results of the Needs Analysis and Suggestions for Japanese Language Teacher Akper Bethesda Tomohon.

In terms of subject and content, the instructor advocates for teaching materials that are authentic and tailored to the students' needs and majors. This ensures that the materials serve as a practical resource aligned with the students' majors, fostering genuine interest. For Japanese teaching materials in nursing, the instructor recommends the inclusion of the four language skills, *kaiwa* (conversation), and *bunpou* (grammar), along with a list of new words (*atarashii kotoba*), visuals, and insights into Japanese culture. Emphasizing the importance of an engaging textbook, the instructor highlights the significance of cultivating communicative language skills from an early stage.

Regarding the completeness of teaching materials, the instructor suggests incorporating dialogues, vocabulary list visuals, grammar explanations, verb lists with variations, teacher and student instructions, and answer keys. This ensures that the textbook is both interesting and clear. In terms of topics and content, the instructor advises selecting topics that stimulate students' creativity, adapting subject matter to learners' experiences. Specific recommendations include incorporating practical examples for each language skill, such as workplace conversations for speaking skills (*kaiwa*) and room-related translations for reading material (*dokkai*). Respondents also provided examples for each skill, such as conversations with superiors for speaking skills, conversations during travel for listening (*choukai*), translating room parts for reading material, and writing descriptions of daily work activities for writing material (*sakubun*). Vocabulary material (*Goi*) is proposed to include nursing-related words, while grammar (*bunpou*) should cover polite forms and sentence patterns.

For textbooks in general, the emphasis is on including numerous dialogues and clear instructions for students. The rationale is to provide ample examples for practicing speaking skills and evaluating comprehension through various question formats. Specifically for *Kaiwa* (conversation) material, the suggestion is to include explanations and descriptions of real situations, considering the context, conditions, and abilities of students. This should be accompanied by instructions on how to listen to the dialogue and answer questions for precision and clarity.

For listening material (*choukai*), students should receive instructions on listening to dialogues and answering related questions. Additionally, students can be asked to retell the dialogue or practice what they heard on a cassette or CD. In reading materials (*dokkai*), instructions for teachers and students are essential. The material should be diverse, incorporating dialogues, narratives, or discourses, followed by questions for comprehension. Answers to these questions should be provided for guidance and correction.

The holistic approach to Japanese teaching materials involves integrating all four language skills in one book, with each skill section separated for focused learning. The difficulty level of grammar and vocabulary should align with students' mastery levels, progressing from basic to advanced. Regarding gradation, the consensus among respondents is the necessity of organizing textbooks systematically, moving from simple to complex or from easiest to most difficult. This gradation aligns with progressive stages of learning, with topics arranged from highly familiar to less familiar

to optimize student understanding. Vocabulary (Goi) in the four skills (choukai, kaiwa, dokkai, and pocketbun) should follow a gradation from easy to difficult. Similarly, for grammar (bunpou), the four skills should be organized in a graduated fashion from easy to difficult.

The Results of the Analysis of Interviews with Users, Namely the Nursing Home in Japan.

The interview results highlighted that students participating in the internship program are required to possess proficiency in writing and reading hiragana, katakana, and basic Kanji characters. Furthermore, there is a strong emphasis on the expectation that prospective internship participants should demonstrate the ability to compose written and oral reports related to their duties and responsibilities. This is particularly crucial concerning daily activities and work responsibilities, coupled with a mastery of nursing practices. Analyzing the data gathered through triangulation of information from students, teachers, and users, a consistent theme emerged—there is a unanimous need for teaching materials aligned with the field of nursing, specifically in the context of Japanese language learning. Users express a keen desire for nursing graduates who not only excel in their field but are also proficient in Japanese.

Derived from the outcomes of the needs analysis, a conclusive finding emerged that necessitates the development of teaching materials tailored to the requirements of the Nursing department. Subsequently, Japanese language teaching materials were crafted, drawing insights from various theories related to language teaching material development, adhering to established principles, and paying meticulous attention to specific purposes. The development process followed the model proposed by Jolly and Bolitho for language teaching material development.

Japanese Language Teaching Material Design for Nursing Students Program Internship

Draft Model

The draft I model of Japanese teaching materials for nursing students is prepared after the needs analysis activity, namely through the results of triangulation analysis types of needs from three different sources of information, namely students, teachers/lecturers and users (triangulation of sources) as well as through observation, interviews and questionnaires (technical triangulation).

Besides being based on needs analysis, this model is also prepared based on the principles of developing teaching materials models according to Nunan in (Tomlinson (Ed.), 2007) which is packaged in six principles and criteria, namely:

- 1) Having a clear relationship with the curriculum,
- 2) Being authentic in relation to texts and assignments
- 3) Encouraging and fostering interaction.
- 4) Provide opportunities for learners to focus on the formal aspects of language.
- 5) Encourage students to develop skills in learning, and
- 6) Encourage students to apply their skills in the real world they work.

Based on hAs a result of the analysis of the components of the research mentioned above, a design for the development of the Japanese School of Nursing teaching materials model was formulated for the internship program which consists of four structural components, three main components and sub-components. The four structural components are:

- 1) Introduction,
- 2) Competence,
- 3) Orientation, and
- 4) Evaluation.

The two main components are: the nursing component and the language skills component. The next sub-component is the description of language skills in sub-sub-topics and various activities/activities in teaching materials.

Model Design

Model 1 draft of Teaching Materials Developed after needs Analysis.

This draft I model contains:

Introduction

This introduction appears at the beginning of each material as a guide for students before entering the topic or core of the learning material. This introduction contains an overview and can be in the form of question sentences that can stimulate students to immediately want to know new material.

Competence

Competence is the final ability or learning goal that will be obtained by students after each subject is completed, which is stated in the form of learning objectives.

Orientation

Orientation is a description of the material or content of learning materials for each topic or subject. The description contains all the material studied in a comprehensive unit covering four language skills and linguistic aspects, namely vocabulary and grammar. Each topic or subject in the teaching materials contains material related to Nursing. Furthermore, the description of the contents in this orientation section is explained as follows: At the beginning, it begins with listening activities (choukai) via video/CD which contains vocabulary introduction in the form of short conversations. Then talk through the conversation (Kaiwa). Furthermore, Vocabulary through understanding new words and expressions (atarashii kotoba), which also includes reading. After that, grammar goes through various forms of sentence patterns, and is followed by writing. Writing in the form of a short discourse which is implemented through a test. It can be stated here that the scope of various skills such as speaking, listening, reading, writing as well as other linguistic aspects such as vocabulary and grammar are indeed not explicitly written per section, but all of them are contained in the form of command sentences in certain sections because they are The target of this teaching material is the ability to communicate.

The model of teaching materials developed in this initial draft is part I or lesson I, where the content of the subject matter is greetings and introductions. Therefore, the topic is divided into two sub-topics, namely A. Greetings, and B. Introductions. However,

before entering the core material section, starting in lesson I, the earliest starts with writing hiragana and katakana.

Evaluation

Evaluation activities are carried out to determine the extent of the achievement of the learning process and to determine the ability of students to understand the material that has just been studied. Evaluation or assessment is carried out while the teaching and learning process takes place and at the end of the lesson.

Draft II

After the draft 1 model was made, it was tested in small groups of six students. After the trial, it will get sufficient input for the improvement of the developed model. Students' opinions about the draft 1 teaching material model are as follows:

- 1) The model of teaching materials is good because it uses videos that can be seen directly.
- 2) The material is interesting because there are Japanese writings (hiragana and katakana)
- 3) The topic is very suitable for nursing majors, especially topics in daily life in nursing homes
- 4) Exercise is good because it is immediately practiced (more in the form of role play)
- 5) Need more time for practice,
- 6) need simple kanji,
- 7) The model is good because it uses a lot of pictures, and
- 8) Test directly during conversation practice.

Opinions, suggestions and input from students through limited group trials can be stated that basically the teaching materials developed are good as in points 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7, while points 5 and 6 are input about pens. The ingredients for kanji are simple and need extra time for practice. Based on the input above, a phase I revision was carried out.

After the phase I revision is carried out, then validation is carried out through an expert feasibility test or *expert judgment*. Those involved in this due diligence are experts in the field of Japanese language and Japanese language teaching methodology.

Input or expert opinion obtained based on the validation test is presented qualitatively as follows:

1. The order of the material is arranged in order
2. Each lesson is arranged based on the time allocation that has been set
3. We recommend using abstract images that are in accordance with the learning objectives
4. We recommend using vocabulary that is closely related to the vocational; such as: Nyuuyoku, Kigae, Kurumaisu, and others
5. The explanation for the word san is written similar to the word "sang" in Indonesian
6. should be separated between vocabulary, explanation and material.

7. Consistency of writing, such as the use of punctuation marks to pay attention to
8. The material is different from the grammatical explanation. Materials must be prepared in accordance with the approach and ready-to-use forms.
9. Write Captions on pictures of people. For example: Nihon jin desu. Then write a nickname on each person's picture.
10. Instructions in practice must be written clearly
11. Examples of commands in hanashite mimashou, write: tomodachi to aisatsu shite Kudasai.

Observing the expert input above, it can be stated that in general it is more technical in nature, such as the location of the presentation order, writing orders, using appropriate vocabulary and writing descriptions on pictures.

Based on the input obtained after expert validation, the authors revise again by developing a unit of study by taking a different topic. This was done because the learning material in topic I above is an introduction to Japanese language material (so we will not use Hiragana and Katakana letters yet. Furthermore, based on expert input, a revision was made to improve teaching materials so as to produce draft II. The changes are very prominent is in terms of the use of letters in teaching materials.

The writing of teaching materials in the draft I model only uses Romaji letters while in the second draft model the teaching materials use three types of letters, namely; Romaji, Hiragana and Katakana. Furthermore, The topics shown are chapter ten (10) learning materials which means that the lessons of hiragana and katakana have been completed in the previous lesson. This change was made at the student's suggestion after testing in a limited group, and setting the instructions and the order of the material proposed by the expert.

Final Model

After going through various stages of trials and expert tests, the final model or final Japanese language teaching materials for Nursing students participating in the internship program at Japanese nursing homes are produced. Basically, the draft that has been prepared previously (draft II) has not undergone significant changes in the final model. In this final model, what is more clarified are the activity steps which are a sub-section of the activities that are passed which are described in detail.

Model Eligibility

AppropriatenessThe model was carried out after a small (limited) group trial was held. and after revision of the input obtained from the test results. The feasibility test of the model is carried out by asking for opinions, suggestions for improvements and suggestions from experts.

The expert who tested or validated the teaching materials developed was Frangky R. Nayoan, MA. PHD. experts in the field of Japanese language and Japanese language teaching methodology. The expert validation test is carried out when the developed teaching material model is ready to be tested again in the real class. Thus, expert input becomes very useful for the next stage of improvement for the improvement of the model.

The validation test of the developed teaching materials includes two main components, namely:

- 1) Teaching Material Prototype, and
- 2) Instructions, illustrations, pictures and so on.

In the prototype section of teaching materials, it consists of seven aspects, namely

1. The objective aspect which includes the suitability of the purpose and the appearance of the goal,
2. The command aspect includes the command display, the location of the command and the content of the command,
3. The material aspect includes the suitability of the topic with the field of study, the relationship of the material with objectives, sequencing of materials, and content of lessons.
4. Aspects of using teaching methods,
5. Assessment, and
6. Practice questions.

Of the six aspects assessed, only three aspects received input for improvement, namely:

- 1) The command aspect so that the instructions or tasks to be carried out by students were more clarified.
- 2) Sorting the arrangement of material where there needs to be a clear separation between vocabulary, explanation, and material, as well as arrangement according to the approach in a ready-to-use form.
- 3) The use of vocabulary in the content of the subject matter, it is recommended to use vocabulary that is closely related to vocational or work (Lakes & Donovan, 2018).

In the second component, which is about instructions, illustrations, pictures and others, expert input is in the image section so that information is added. It is also recommended to use abstract images. Based on expert input, the teaching materials developed are improved In the second component, which is about instructions, illustrations, pictures and others, expert input is in the image section so that information is added.

It is also recommended to use abstract images. Based on expert input, the teaching materials developed are improved In the second component, which is about instructions, illustrations, pictures and others, expert input is in the image section so that information is added. It is also recommended to use abstract images. Based on expert input, the teaching materials developed are improved

Expert assessments and input in the form of comments, suggestions, criticisms in the form of qualitative data obtained through discussions and consultations.

In general, based on the expert's assessment, it can be concluded that the product of Japanese Nursing teaching materials is good so that it is feasible to use. However, there are some suggestions for improving teaching material products.

The components of the prototype teaching materials that need to be revised are the clarity of the contents of the instructions, and a clear separation of vocabulary, explanations, and materials. While the other inputs are just for display and all the inputs have been implemented.

Model Effectiveness

After the expert validation test has been carried out, the developed teaching material model has met the eligibility requirements. Furthermore, to determine the effectiveness of the model, the effectiveness of the model was tested. Model testing was carried out in two ways, namely: firstly, implementing teaching materials in Japanese language learning classes at Akper Bethesda in the form of experiments using a pretest posttest design, and secondly, testing the effectiveness of readability and student and teacher perceptions of the model developed through a questionnaire.

Effectiveness Test Through Experiments and Using the t Test

The model's effectiveness test was conducted in the Nursing class. The researcher taught in the experimental class using the developed teaching materials. After the learning process is complete, a test is held.

Furthermore, the value of the results obtained is compared with the values obtained by using the teaching materials in Akper and tested using the statistical formula t test. Based on the posttest results following the implementation of the developed Japanese teaching materials in the experimental class, the average score was 81.61. In contrast, the average score obtained using the teaching materials at Akper was 66.39. Subsequently, a t-test was conducted using both SPSS 25 and manual calculations.

The table above is interpreted as follows: the calculated t-value is 4.595. Upon comparing this value with the critical t-value at a significance level of 0.05 with degrees of freedom (df) equal to 34, it is evident that the calculated t-value (4.595) surpasses the critical t-value (2.021). Therefore, a significant difference in the average student learning outcomes is observed between those using conventional teaching materials and those using the developed teaching materials.

The average learning outcomes of students utilizing the developed teaching materials are notably higher than those using materials at Akper. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis (H_a). These results suggest that the tested teaching materials exhibit a high level of effectiveness. In conclusion, the developed Japanese Nursing teaching materials are deemed both feasible and effective for use by Nursing students participating in internship programs at Japanese Nursing Homes.

Test of Readability and Perceptions of Students and Teachers of Japanese Nursing Teaching Material Models

The readability test was conducted to determine the perceptions of students and teachers of the teaching materials developed using a questionnaire instrument containing twenty-eight items. The questionnaire that was run using a Likert scale contained four categories of choices, namely strongly agree, very feasible, very relevant, very good (SS), Agree, decent, relevant, good (ST), less agree, less feasible, less relevant, less good (KS), and disagree, inappropriate, irrelevant, not good (TS).

This readability and perception test covers 16 aspects, namely:

- 1) Connected to the curriculum,
- 2) There are clear instructions,
- 3) Encouraging and fostering interaction,
- 4) Focusing on language,
- 5) Application of learning skills,
- 6) Encouraging their application in the world. real,
- 7) Relevance aspect,
- 8) Meets psychological validity
- 9) Meets / has pedagogical validity, and
- 10) Meets process and content validity and uses an up to date methodology.,
- 11) Potential for affective engagement,
- 12) Interesting and fun,
- 13) Paying attention to the desired learning motivation,
- 14) Following a gradual and correct sequence,
- 15) Applying a communication approach such as feedback, and so on, and
- 16) The availability of tests that are in accordance with the material given. The sixteen aspects above are described in 28 questions through a questionnaire.

The number of students involved in the readability test of teaching materials was 18 people, namely students who were used as the experimental class. Furthermore, the perception and assessment of Japanese language teachers at Akper were also asked. The perceptions and assessments of incoming students and teachers are added up and then presented in a percentage according to the specified aspects. The percentage results data on the readability assessment through student perceptions above is then shown in **Table 5** below.

Table 5: Results of the Readability Test of Nursing Japanese Teaching Materials Through Student Perception.

No.	Principles Of Teaching Materials And Aspects Of Reading Test	Average Percentage			
		SS	ST	KS	TS
1	Teaching materials must have a clear relationship with the curriculum used	64,22	35,78		
2	There are instructions for follow-up or general progress of learning	64,22	35,78		
3	Teaching materials must encourage and foster interaction	59.40	40,60		
4	Teaching materials must provide opportunities for learners to focus on the formal aspects of language	70.31	29,61		
5	Teaching materials encourage students to develop various skills in learning	58.55	41,45		
6	Teaching materials must encourage students to apply their skills in the real world	99	1,0		
7	Teaching materials must be relevant, consistent, and sufficient	98	12		
8	Fulfilling psychological validity in the form of student needs and helping free learning and encouraging student autonomy in	55.56	44.44		

No.	Principles Of Teaching Materials And Aspects Of Reading Test	Average Percentage			
		SS	ST	KS	TS
	order to develop effective learning strategies.				
9	Meets pedagogical validity; it means that the textbook shows a sufficient measure of compatibility with the skills and abilities of the teacher.	65.40	34.60		
10	Meets process and content validity. the methodology is up to date, the content of the material is appropriate, has appropriateness and is authentic, culturally sensitive, the layout and design is clear, easy to obtain, flexible, and complete, and can provide opportunities for students to be skilled in interpretation so that it is challenging to think higher critically.	77.78	22.22		
11	Has the potential for affective engagement	70.00	30.00		
12	Can be used with fun both by students and by teachers.	69.45	30.55		
13	Pay attention to the desired learning motivation	66.67	33.33		
14	Following a gradual and correct sequence	60	40		
15	Can provide feedback	44.14	55.86		
16	There are tests that are in accordance with the material given	40,88	59.11		

Furthermore, the teacher's perceptions obtained on the questions described in 28 items are as follows. All 27 items were answered strongly agree, very worthy, very relevant, or very good (96.43%), and only one item answered agree, deserve, relevant, or good (3.57%). This means that the teaching materials developed are good and even very good and relevant according to the teacher's opinion.

Based on the results of the readability test both through student perceptions and teacher perceptions as stated above, it can be explained that almost all of them reach 100% when combined for the category of strongly agree, very good, very relevant (SS) and good category, agree, relevant (ST). .

Thus, it can be stated that the Japanese Nursing teaching materials that have been developed are feasible and effective to be used for Akper students. Learning by using trialed teaching materials makes the class very lively, students are passionate, very motivated and even very enthusiastic in learning so that the achievements achieved are greatly increased because the teaching materials used answer the needs of students in the field of nursing.

DISCUSSION

The development of this teaching material model has been conducted in accordance with the research objectives and through extensive stages aligned with the mechanisms and development steps. Furthermore, this study was crafted based on a need's analysis derived from triangulation involving three distinct sources, namely, student feedback and input from users in Japanese nursing homes. The merits and strengths of the developed teaching material model are attributed to its foundation in the results of a needs analysis. This approach ensures that the teaching materials possess the following characteristics:

- 1) Tailored for specific purposes;
- 2) Focused on addressing the requirements of nursing work in the elderly care sector.

Consequently, these teaching materials effectively motivate students to engage in independent or group study, with teachers playing a facilitative role.

Based on the explanation above, it can be stated that the model of Japanese language teaching materials for elderly nursing which was developed in accordance with the needs analysis is very suitable for use by students participating in the program (Kim et al., 2016). *Internship* and it can even be used in schools or nursing departments because in many ways it has been adapted to the nursing field. In addition, the teaching materials developed have been validated by Japanese language experts and Japanese language teaching methodologies, and have been tested for effectiveness. Thus, this teaching material model can be recommended as a Japanese language teaching material model that can be used by the nursing department.

Therefore, it can be asserted that the development of effective and engaging teaching materials needs to be continually pursued to encourage learners to be more active, creative, and enhance their learning enthusiasm, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes (Ratta, 2015). This is evident during the final phase testing of the developed teaching material model, intended to assess its effectiveness. It was found that almost all students were able to complete tasks and answer questions correctly.

CONCLUSIONS

The needs analysis revealed a shared demand among students, teachers, and users for teaching materials tailored to the specific requirements of the nursing department, particularly in the context of elderly care. Subsequently, a model of Japanese teaching materials was developed, guided by established principles for developing language teaching materials and aligned with the objectives of creating materials for specific purposes. Following expert tests and effectiveness assessments, it is affirmed that the Japanese language teaching material model for nursing students engaged in the Internship program is effective. The effectiveness test, conducted through a questionnaire distributed to students and teachers, demonstrated positive feedback. Notably, 53.77% of students strongly agreed, 46.03% agreed, and 0.198% disagreed with the quality of the teaching materials. Among teachers, 96.429% strongly agreed, and 3.571% agreed. Collectively, 95% of respondents, comprising both teachers and students, rated the developed teaching materials as good or very good.

Based on this feedback, it can be concluded that the developed teaching materials are both feasible and effective for use in the Nursing Department, particularly for participants in the Internship program at Japanese nursing homes affiliated with the Bethesda Tomohon Nursing Academy. The developed model is anticipated to have implications for the competency of Japanese language teachers, emphasizing the importance of employing effective methods. The model encourages student engagement and creativity, necessitating proactive efforts from teachers to enhance their capabilities and foster innovation. Recommendations include extending the development of teaching material models for Japanese or other foreign languages, especially tailored for learners with specific purposes such as those in institutions or vocational schools, grounded in thorough needs analyses.

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